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ORCID AND DATACITE
INTEROPERABILITY NETWORK

<http://odin-project.eu>

D5.2 Final roadmap and recommendations for the missing thin layer of the e- Infrastructure

WP5 – Strategy

V1_0

Final

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	WP5: Strategy		Dissemination level: PU
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Abstract: During the ODIN project several steps have been taken to study the missing pieces for an interoperable PID infrastructure. Building on stakeholder specific SWOT analysis and a concise gap analysis from the first project year, a three-pronged approach was taken to update the results to the quickly changing landscape of PIDs and their implementations. The approach comprised web review as well as engagement with PID users at selected events and dedicated interviews with PID experts and practitioners.

As the core results, this report presents a final roadmap consisting of a gap analysis including a progress report on how well these gaps are addressed already and recommendations to build the missing thin layer to enable an interoperable PID infrastructure. The report concludes with recommended actions to address the main gaps.

The analysis highlights that the gaps must be addressed urgently and mainly in a collaborative manner. An open, global and interoperable PID layer could unlock the full potential of Open Science if all stakeholder groups and disciplines are involved.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Turn-of the century concerns about the “data deluge” in science are transforming into discussions of how “data sharing” can be supported in research communities around the globe. These communities require immediate access to research data, and at the same time expect that sharing platforms and services are trusted, secure, and provide long-term data storage and preservation. These services have come to increasingly rely on persistent identifiers (PIDs). PIDs can serve as a connector across platforms - independent of amongst others software environments, technical dependencies of the data and the human beings involved - and are emerging an enabler of Open Science.

In a very fragmented landscape of PIDs for research objects and persons ODIN clarified the promise of an interoperable PID infrastructure, and identified the gaps and barriers to realizing this infrastructure. In its first project year, ODIN developed a gap analysis and defined a roadmap for creating an interoperable PID infrastructure. In this analysis, we found that PIDs are considered useful but are far from being widely implemented and used in Europe. Our approach was to work with the community to identify general and specific needs for PID-based services and reduce barriers to implementation.

In the second year of the ODIN Project, we focused on the roadmap, the way ahead. As a pre-requisite for Open Science, an interoperable PID infrastructure needs to become reality. We have followed a three-pronged approach toward this goal:

- personal interviews with a diverse set of stakeholders,
- conference attendance and presentations, and
- review of web resources

Our report is intended for all stakeholders involved in digital scholarly communication, to further the implementation and usage of PIDs in support of data sharing and Open Science. Chapter 2 present the approach we used to produce the result presented in this

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report. We refined our initial gap analysis and roadmap¹ (D5.1) which is summarized in chapter 3 together with feedback from the 1st year event and input from a panel discussion organised by the project at the Open Repositories conference. In addition, we reviewed several implementations of PIDs in various systems in different environments. Together with the results of the work in the ODIN WP 3 and 4, those implementations are presented in chapter 4. Chapter 5 combines the results from chapter 3 and 4 with conclusions from expert interviews and presents all the input collected during ODIN divided by key stakeholder sections. Chapter 6 outlines the final ODIN gap analysis and the recommendations on how to fill these gaps. Finally, chapter 7 looks ahead and sketches the concluding recommendations of this report.

2. APPROACH

This report takes as its starting point our D5.1 Gap analysis and draft roadmap, which identified ten gaps for the delivery of an interoperable PID infrastructure and stakeholder specific recommendations on how to close them. In addition, three main actions were defined: the delivery of a high-quality interoperable PID layer as well as support of research on missing aspects of a global e-Infrastructure and the development of sustainable and participative business models (see chapter 3.1. for an extensive summary of D5.1).

During the ensuing project year, ODIN partners tracked developments in PID research, technologies, and implementations. Furthermore, ODIN partners contributed to the current landscape of PID interoperability in several ways. D3.3 Proof of Concepts and Communality describes the development of a generic workflow for PID assignment in data submission processes, based on the disciplinary proofs of concepts ODIN created in

¹ ODIN Consortium, Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, and Salvatore Mele. (2013). D5.1 Gap analysis and draft roadmap. Figshare. doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.825546

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the first project year.² D4.2 Workflow for Interoperability demonstrates the added value of PID systems linking research information across systems through key use cases and practical examples of PID interoperability. In addition, several ODIN partners presented at the Open Repositories conference in Helsinki in June 2014.

While we have made progress in raising awareness of the opportunities afforded Open Science by an interoperable PID infrastructure, much more needs to be done to ensure PID services are brought into operation and then made broadly available to both researchers and implementing organizations. We clarified these community needs through interviews with experts and practitioners working with PIDs.

Figure 1 visualizes the three-pronged approach consisting of the conference attendances (incl. the first year event organised by the project), desktop research and the input from the other ODIN WPs as well as the interviews with experts and practitioners.

² ODIN Consortium, John Kaye, Tom Demeranville, and Steven McEachern. (2013). D3.1 Humanities and Social Science Proof of Concept. Figshare. doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.824317

ODIN Consortium, Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Salvatore Mele, Sergio Ruiz, and Simeon Warner. (2013). D3.2 Proof of Concept HEP. Figshare. doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.824315

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Figure 1: Visualisation of ODIN D5.2 approach

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We adjusted the stakeholder groups and representatives of key PID implementations to the attendees of the 1st year event and conferences and our interviewees:

- **Funders and policy makers** have an interest in facilitating an interoperable PID infrastructure to track funding outputs, enable portfolio analysis, and ultimately optimise investment of public funds in research on a national and international scale.
- **Publishers** support the dissemination of findings to the research community, which depends upon discoverability within and across platforms and with the rise in importance of data sharing, also in linking findings to data, contributors, and funders. These business needs are facilitated by an interoperable PID infrastructure
- **e-Infrastructure providers** are key stakeholders in developing an interconnected framework of data-intensive research and scholarship. They serve community needs whilst implementing general standards, and are increasingly complemented by third-party providers of value-added services such as impact assessment. This stakeholder group includes data centres as well as national or institutional repositories and initiatives such as ORCID and DataCite.

In addition to these stakeholders, we also engaged with the geosciences and life sciences communities, as those disciplines are leading in some implementation of PIDs, and are not directly covered in the limited number of the ODIN consortium partners. This stakeholder approach was already successfully applied in the first year of the project and resulted in D5.1.

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Interview methodology

To collect requirements regarding identifiers, implementations, and linking between identifier platforms, we engaged with PID experts and practitioners. Our list of PID experts was drawn from a review of the literature and collaborations of the ODIN project partners. From an original list of 25 names, 6 people were eventually contacted for interviews. These experts cover all stakeholder groups and provide cross-disciplinary experiences from several nations. The interviews were conducted using videoconferencing systems such as Skype and Vidyo and usually lasted about one hour.

When contacted for an interview, the interviewees were provided with a short briefing document summarizing the ODIN project, including the findings of the first-year WP5 gap analysis. The interviews were semi-structured interviews, in which we provided the experts with questions in advance. These questions served as a guideline for the interviews; however, depending on the interviewee's experiences and insights the questions were adapted or not asked if they were not applicable. The briefing document including the questionnaire for the semi-structured interviews can be found in Annex II. The notes from the interviews were sent to the interviewees for approval to ensure they were not misquoted. The interview transcripts are available to the project partners on the project twiki. As they are impossible to anonymize, the transcripts will not be published in the annex.

Conference attendances

To spread the ODIN results as widely as possible, ODIN partners attended several conferences.³ There, they engaged with the audience to gather feedback on ODIN work and PID related gaps and challenges. Furthermore, the conferences were a great source to learn about new PID implementations.

³ An overview of the conference attendances can be found in D2.4 Final communication report including results from final event

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Review of web resources

The project partners thoroughly monitored mailing lists as well as twitter accounts of practitioners working with PIDs and initiatives engaged in data sharing and data citation using PIDs. In addition, web information retrieval was carried out to find more PID implementations.

3. THE ROADMAP SO FAR - WHAT DO WE BUILD ON

The starting point for the final roadmap and recommendations is the gap analysis and draft roadmap provided after the first project year. The ten gaps and recommendations presented in D5.1 are summarized in this chapter. In addition, we present the feedback we gathered through conference attendances focusing on the first year event organised by the project and the ODIN panel discussion at the Open Repositories conference in Helsinki in June 2014.

3.1. Overview of D5.1

The main output of D5.1 Gap analysis and draft roadmap was the identification of 10 gaps for providing an interoperable PID infrastructure. In the first year interim report, we provided a list of actions to be taken to bridge these gaps. These recommendations are refined in this report based on the expert interviews. Table 1 summarizes the gaps and recommended actions identified in this interim report.

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Table 1: Summary of D5.1 gaps and recommendations

Gap	Action
There is only limited access to PID e-Infrastructures for small organisations.	<i>Lower access barriers for institutions to participate to interoperable global PID e-Infrastructures, through appropriate agreements between institutions, fostering collaborations and with the support of national/international bodies.</i>
Some research communities have little to no experience with interoperable PIDs for data and contributors.	<i>Support those scientific communities without existing PID solutions to participate to existing interoperable PID frameworks, while tailoring interfaces to the specificity of the community.</i>
Local, tailored, PID systems, with no interoperable options, are emerging.	<i>Facilitate interoperability between stakeholders with community-specific, institution-specific or national PIDs solutions and emerging global open solutions.</i>
There is a lack of support and funding to implement international interoperable PID solutions.	<i>Provide (seed) funding to ease local participation and access to emerging PID infrastructures.</i>
Methods and tools to track re-use of research data and other scholarly materials are lacking.	<i>Develop an interoperable PID infrastructure that supports development of third-party tools for discoverability, impact assessment, and other value added services.</i>
Policies to encourage data sharing and acknowledge data re-use in research assessment are not yet widespread.	<i>Design policies to elevate data to a key indicator in research assessment, with appropriate attribution to their creators and curators, through implementation</i>

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Gap	Action
	<i>and usage of open and interoperable PIDs.</i>
Reliable discovery services for research data and non-text based scholarly materials are missing.	<i>Harmonize formats and APIs, so that information from emerging and existing PID frameworks can be exposed and mutually enriched, while enabling third-party discovery services.</i>
Incentives for making datasets re-usable are unclear or missing.	<i>Design appropriate incentive systems to pervade research evaluation, e.g. citation mechanisms based on PIDs for data, linked to PIDs for contributors.</i>
Value-added services that can incentivize citation and open science cannot be built for lack of a widespread, interoperable, PID infrastructure.	<i>Assure that a trusted, open and sustainable interoperable PID infrastructure is established with ease of participation of third-parties.</i>
Unique attribution and linking between researchers, their scholarly materials and funding is just not possible, without a collaborative adoption of global and interoperable PID systems.	<i>Establish a participative framework with PIDs for contributors and materials, where any participant can expose information, enriching the entire e-Infrastructure.</i>

To address these gaps, input from all stakeholder groups is needed. Three overarching actions were identified as part of D5.1:

1. The delivery of a high-quality interoperable PID layer, connecting data and contributors, which can foster the integration of PID implementation efforts of early adopters, third party services, and existing PID workflows.

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2. The promotion and support of multi-stakeholder research on missing aspects of a global PID e-infrastructure. The dialogue between several stakeholders allows the identification of features that need to be developed to benefit stakeholders and facilitate third-party integrations.
3. The design and implementation of sustainable and participative business models. These models should lower the barrier to participate in a global PID e-infrastructure while assuring openness and sustainable operations.

The gaps and actions provided in Table 1 provide the starting point for the results presented in chapters 5 and 6. In addition, overarching targets will be re-defined in the roadmap presented in this report.

3.2. Feedback from first year event at CERN

In October 2013, the ODIN Project organized a first year event⁴ at CERN to review progress and to elicit specific input on the ongoing work. ODIN partners presented the first results of the projects. Workflows produced as part of the proofs of concept were shown as live demonstrations. For WP5, the interim gap analysis and draft roadmap were presented. The DIGOIDUNA experts⁵ presented their feedback and confirmed the existing gaps and the different needs for actions. A dedicated session focused on disciplinary practices and needs allowed a more detailed discussion of the D5.1 analysis. The following disciplines were represented in this discussion:

⁴ Programme and more information can be found at <http://indico.cern.ch/event/238868/other-view?view=standard#20131015>

⁵ As agreed in the DoW, one of the authors of the EC-funded DIGOIDUNA study on the role of identifiers for digital objects and authors will carry out an independent review of the results of the first year of the project as well as a comparative analysis of the final findings of ODIN with the DIGOIDUNA recommendations.

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- Archaeology
- Genomics/Biomedicine
- Humanities and Social Sciences
- Geosciences/Oceanography

The presentations revealed astonishing similarities with regard to persistent identification of data objects and workflows for data preservation and sharing, notably how to assign PIDs and when, how to engage researchers, and when to reuse scenarios, and how to support data citation. This validated the feasibility of our draft recommendations for a cross-disciplinary approach. In practical terms, this feedback was integrated into the year 2 analysis of WP3 - where the commonalities between the two disciplines High Energy Physics (HEP) and Humanities and Social Sciences (HSS) were analysed. The discussions highlighted that, even though concrete future planning was in flux, long-term vision of an interoperable framework for sharing research data was aligned fairly well across disciplines: link people, their research data and publication outputs, and when possible also the supporting organizations.

Presentations about *altmetrics* and the challenges of Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) underlined the need for open PIDs and interoperable platforms to enable third party services. Again, a PID framework was seen as an enabler for interdisciplinary services, on top of disciplinary (data) publishing outlets.

The discussions of the first year event underlined that there are many ongoing or emerging initiatives on disciplinary layer and across disciplines. For researchers to use PIDs, they need to be embedded in seamless Open Science services that are integrated into their regular research tools and workflows, without adding extra reporting burden. In summary, there was general agreement that interoperable PIDs have the potential to link existing and emerging services and thus enable smoother Open Science workflows.

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3.3. Input from the panel discussion at the Open Repositories 2014

The ODIN project organized a panel, “Promoting Interoperability and Services Through Shared Identifiers”, at the Open Repositories (OR) conference in Helsinki on June 12th 2014⁶ to elicit a discussion about the usage of PIDs in repository systems, beyond those studied in WP3 and WP4 in ODIN. The technical leads of ORCID and DataCite started off the panel with an overview of the organisations and recent developments. Then, PID implementations and challenges from Dryad and the HEP proof of concept were shown. The lively discussion⁷ highlighted several topics that deserve special attention in future work and further support the gaps identified in the interviews:

- Business models: How can small scale institutions get easy access to ORCID services?
- Sustainability: Can we rely on DataCite services? What happens if DataCite cannot sustain its services in the future?
- Costs: Which is the value of ORCID membership when ORCID iDs are free? Why are not DOIs for free?
- Interoperability: How does DataCite interoperate with other PID systems?
- DOI naming conventions: How do we address versioning of data sets and expose versions to users?
- Implementation support: Are widgets or plugins planned to enable an easy integration of ORCID iDs/DOIs into more repository systems?

OR attendees have experience with PIDs, but the panel discussion highlighted the need for better integration support, improved and more targeted outreach materials, and means to share experiences. Taken together with the interview comments, there appears

⁶ Abstract available at https://www.conftool.com/or2014/index.php?page=browseSessions&form_session=101

⁷ The session was recorded and can be watched at <https://connectpro.helsinki.fi/p1i8feahljq/>

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to be an urgent need for capacity building, both in regards to technical documentation and support, and for the administrative or management aspects of PID services implementations.

4. REVIEW OF RECENT DEVELOPMENTS

In addition to the engagement at conferences, we carried out desktop research to keep up to date with PID implementations. As the topic of PID interoperability is a moving target, it is important to follow recent developments to see if some of the D5.1 gaps are already closed and to spot new challenges. This chapter gives an overview of the PID implementations that happened in the last twelve months. Starting with a report by the ODIN partners ORCID and DataCite, we then give an overview on general PID implementations as well as PID implementations in Higher Education Institutes and a discipline specific report on biomedicine and health research. Furthermore, we summarize the work in WP3 and WP4 as the experience gained there contributed to the final roadmap and recommendations presented in chapter 6.

4.1. CONCEPTUAL IMPLEMENTATION

4.1.1. ORCID and DataCite

ORCID

ORCID launched officially on October 16th 2012, the day before the ODIN project kick-off event in Berlin. Since then, the number of ORCID iDs created by and for researchers has grown dramatically, passing 800,000 in July 2014 (see Figure 2). As of July 28th 2014, there are 4,575,000 research works (e.g., publications, datasets, books) linked to ORCID iDs, with 2,227,000 unique DOIs linked to ORCID records.

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Figure 2: Uptake of ORCID iDs since launch

At the 2014 ORCID spring Outreach Meeting⁸, hosted by the University of Illinois at Chicago, the breadth of ORCID integrations and developments was demonstrated with 32 presentations across two days, showcasing ORCID integrations by professional associations into publication, membership, and meetings systems, and by universities in administrative and access management systems, repositories, and research management and reporting systems.

ORCID has collaborated with data providers to enable researchers to easily connect their works, affiliation, and other identifier information with their ORCID iD. ÜberResearch⁹ developed a search tool¹⁰ to enable researchers to query the ÜberResearch database (which uses the FundRef¹¹ registry to identify funders) and link to their funded awards.

⁸ <https://orcid.org/content/orcid-outreach-meeting-and-codefest-may-2014>

⁹ <http://www.digital-science.com/products/uberresearch>

¹⁰ <http://orcid.org/blog/2014/02/19/link-your-orcid-record-your-funding>

¹¹ <http://www.crossref.org/fundref/>

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Ringgold¹² identifiers are used to enable links with employer and degree-granting institutions. And an ISNI2ORCID wizard¹³ has been launched that enables a user to link their ORCID record with their ISNI, and import metadata for any ISBNs associated with the linked record.

During the lifespan of the ODIN project, ORCID has increasingly become an integral part of the research landscape. Horizon 2020 explicitly mentions ORCID in the EU grants manual¹⁴ as an example of a PID that could be used by researchers; it also recommends the use of DataCite DOIs for datasets.¹⁵ In the EU, ORCID iDs have been integrated in the Wellcome Trust eGrants application system and are a prerequisite for inclusion in research evaluation at the Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia¹⁶ in Portugal, where 97% of grantees have registered an ORCID iD. Furthermore, ORCID iDs have been integrated into publisher manuscript submission and review workflow systems provided by third-party vendors including eJournalPress¹⁷, Aries¹⁸, ScholarOne¹⁹, and Elsevier Editorial System²⁰, another crucial researcher workflow.

ORCID iDs are also being integrated into widely used repository software.²¹ Eprints released a simple plugin in April 2014 that allows the import of works based on an

¹² <http://www.ringgold.com/> provides institutional identifiers and is especially used by publishers

¹³ <http://isni2orcid.labs.orcid-eu.org/>

¹⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

¹⁵ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

¹⁶ http://www.fct.pt/apoios/unidades/avaliacoes/2013/analise_bibliometrica.phtml.en

¹⁷ <http://www.ejournalpress.com/>

¹⁸ <http://www.editorialmanager.com/homepage/home.htm>

¹⁹ <http://scholarone.com/>

²⁰ <http://editorsupdate.elsevier.com/short-communications/unique-orcid-now-available-in-ees/>

²¹ <http://libraryconnect.elsevier.com/articles/2014-06/connecting-researchers-their-research-through-community-adoption-orcid>

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ORCID ID.²² The Invenio²³ based platform Zenodo²⁴ allows users to sign up or in with their ORCID ID since June 2014.²⁵ Integrations are also underway for DSpace, Drupal, Hydra/Fedora, Vireo, VIVO, and others. Many of these tools were demonstrated at the Open Repositories conference.

DataCite

Since the launch of ODIN in fall 2012, DataCite has more than doubled the number of registered DOI names from 1.6 million in October 2012 to 3.5 million in July 2014. Furthermore DataCite has grown its membership to now 22 full members (from 16 in October 2012), 8 affiliate members (5 in October 2012) in total representing 18 countries (compared to 13 in October 2012) from all continents.

DataCite worked on his metadata schema to accommodate more PIDs and thus facilitating interoperability. In February 2014, Version 3.0 of the DataCite Metadata Schema²⁶ was published and now includes:

- ORCID identifiers for scholars and fellow contributors,
- FundRef identifiers for funder information, and
- locations via the World Geodetic System (WGS)²⁷ coordinates

During the lifespan of the ODIN project, DataCite collaborated with several initiatives such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA) where DataCite members are actively engaged

²² <http://bazaar.eprints.org/354/>

²³ <http://invenio-software.org/>

²⁴ <https://zenodo.org/>

²⁵ https://twitter.com/ZENODO_ORG/status/478825591123509248

²⁶ <http://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-3/index.html>

²⁷ <http://earth-info.nga.mil/GandG/wgs84/>

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in working and interest groups and in the organizational advisory board task force of the RDA.

In winter 2013 DataCite was involved in the definition of the “Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles” together with the Force11 group²⁸, the CODATA task group on data citation²⁹, the RDA and other initiatives. The principles were published in spring 2014³⁰ and DataCite was among the first organisations who endorsed them.

By the end of 2015, DataCite will host a merged service of the projects Databib³¹ and “re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories”³² as it was announced in March 2014. The aim of this merger is to reduce duplication of effort and to better serve the research community with a single, sustainable registry of research data repositories that incorporates the best features of both projects. The joint registry will be operated under the name “re3data.org – Registry of Research Data Repositories” with its editorial board retaining the name of Databib. Both registries have posted a Memorandum of Understanding on their respective websites and have exchanged metadata records in advance of fully merging their platforms and processes.³³

Furthermore the largest North American data repository, the Interuniversity Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR)³⁴, moved the DOI names of their 20,000 registered objects from CrossRef to DataCite services. More than 700 academic institutions and research organizations archive their data with ICPSR which provides valuable and comprehensive database for empirical researchers.

²⁸ <http://www.force11.org>

²⁹ <http://www.codata.org/task-groups/data-citation-standards-and-practices>

³⁰ <https://www.force11.org/datacitation>

³¹ <http://databib.org/>

³² <http://www.re3data.org/>

³³ <http://www.re3data.org/2014/03/datacite-re3data-org-databib-collaboration/>

³⁴ <https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/icpsrweb/landing.jsp>

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From summer 2014 on, the scientific network ResearchGate³⁵ is now supporting DataCite DOI names for the scientific content of its members. Through cooperation of ResearchGate, DataCite and DataCite's member TIB (German National Library of Science and Technology)³⁶, scientists can easily integrate DataCite DOI names into their scientific profile. Furthermore they can even register new DOI names if they upload scientific content to ResearchGate. Even more this content can be rated and commented by other ResearchGate members. This presents a unique new opportunity to combine DOI names for scientific content with social network functionalities.³⁷

4.1.2. Interdisciplinary and general developments

The demand has been growing to acknowledge research contributions in addition to journal publications. It is agreed that PIDs, especially DOIs, are a critical component of any citation, and enable navigation back to the source document and harvesting of metadata to support citation. GitHub³⁸ - a software code sharing platform - for example collaborated with Zenodo and figshare³⁹ to enable DOI assignment to code repositories and thus, make code submissions persistent and citable.⁴⁰

Even publishers extend their assignment of DOIs beyond scientific articles. The Open Access publisher PeerJ⁴¹ offers the option for authors to make the peer-reviews of their articles openly available. This feature is well used; so far however, these reviews could only be referred by a unique URL. From May 2014 on, PeerJ assigns DOIs to these

³⁵ <http://www.researchgate.net/>

³⁶ <http://www.tib.uni-hannover.de/en/>

³⁷ <https://news.researchgate.net/index.php?/archives/189-Celebrating-five-million-members-with-free-DOIs.html>

³⁸ <https://github.com/>

³⁹ <http://figshare.com/>

⁴⁰ <https://guides.github.com/activities/citable-code/>

⁴¹ <https://peerj.com/>

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reviews to make it easier for researchers to get credit for all kinds of scientific contributions.⁴² A similar approach is followed by Publons⁴³, a platform that aims at “making peer review faster, more efficient, and more effective.” This should ideally lead to peer reviews also becoming a first class scientific output, thus they assign DOIs to the peer reviews published on the platform to make them citable.⁴⁴ In collaboration with CASRAI, ORCID works on citation structures for peer review activities and linking them to ORCID profiles.⁴⁵

4.1.3. Higher Education Institutes (HEIs)

Many universities and institutional repositories in Europe are exploring ORCID iDs as a means to identify authors unambiguously, and are encouraging their researchers and students to use ORCID iDs. Following a statement by several UK higher education sector stakeholders to support ORCID⁴⁶ in 2013, first integrations of ORCID iDs into databases followed. The UK Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA) for example now includes ORCID iDs in their student records.⁴⁷ JISC and the Association of Research Managers and Administrators (ARMA)⁴⁸ launched an “ORCID pilot project” in March 2014⁴⁹ funding ORCID implementations at UK HEIs. The outputs are expected to be presented in January 2015.

⁴² <http://blog.peerj.com/post/84907052088/peerj-peer-reviews-now-have-dois>
<https://peerj.com/about/FAQ/academic-contribution/>

⁴³ <https://publons.com/>

⁴⁴ <http://blog.publons.com/post/61380784056/announcing-doi-support-for-reviews>

⁴⁵ Haak, L., Baker, D., & Hoellrigl, T. (2014). CASRAI and ORCID: Putting the Pieces together to Collaboratively Support the Research Community. *Procedia Computer Science*. Elsevier BV. doi:10.1016/j.procs.2014.06.045

⁴⁶ <https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/4988/1/ResIDjointstatement.pdf>

⁴⁷ <http://www.hesa.ac.uk/content/view/3126/>

⁴⁸ <https://www.arma.ac.uk/>

⁴⁹ http://www.jisc.ac.uk/fundingopportunities/funding_calls/2014/03/orcid.aspx

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In addition to the UK, Madrid and Catalan universities became active and decided to use ORCID iDs for their researchers to allow the easy aggregation of information from several database systems.⁵⁰ An increasing number of university libraries and institutional repositories all across Europe are aware of the advantages of ORCID iDs and provide guidance and teaching material for researchers on how to get an ORCID iD.

4.1.4. Exemplary discipline specific implementation – Biomedicine & Health research

Following the example of the collaboration between PANGAEA and Elsevier⁵¹, Europe PubMed Central (PMC) launched tools in 2013 to link publications with data, funding, and since May 2014, material from other providers, amongst them the Dryad repository.⁵² The linking allows Europe PMC to track data citations⁵³, but these statistics are not yet made available. In addition to research objects, Europe PMC integrated ORCID in a way that allows authors to link their articles in Europe PMC to their ORCID iD, and also enables search of Europe PMC by ORCID iD.⁵⁴

4.2. REVIEW OF RECENT ODIN WORK: INPUT FROM WP3 AND WP4

The work carried out in WP5 and the gap analysis leading to the preparation of the final roadmap is also interconnected with work packages 3 and 4. WP3 has provided a comprehensive view of the common community requirements for the implementation

⁵⁰ <http://www.csuc.cat/en/press-release/catalan-universities-agree-to-use-the-orcid-identifier-for-their-researchers>

⁵¹ <http://www.elsevier.com/about/press-releases/science-and-technology/elsevier-and-pangaea-link-contents-for-easier-access-to-full-earth-system-research>

⁵² <http://blog.europepmc.org/2014/05/now-available-use-fois-with-our.html>

⁵³ <http://europepmc.org/Help#databasecitations>

⁵⁴ http://europepmc.org/docs/Europe_PMC_Annual_Report_2013.pdf

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and use of an interoperable PID infrastructure for research data and contributor identifiers, through an analysis of pertinent workflows for the humanities and social sciences (HSS)⁵⁵, using the NSHD (National Survey of Health and Development),⁵⁶ UKDA (UK Data Archive),⁵⁷ and ADS (Archaeology Data Service)⁵⁸ repositories as case studies; and high energy physics (HEP)⁵⁹ using INSPIRE services.⁶⁰ This analysis validated the PID infrastructure analysis presented in WP4 (see below). In the present deliverable, we integrate the findings from WP3 and WP4 into our final recommendations.

By examining the technical and cultural commonalities and differences, WP3 led to the description of concrete data management workflows. WP3 partners focussed on the intervention points for the assignment of DataCite DOIs and ORCID iDs throughout the data management process. Their analysis revealed the areas that require improvement within the DataCite and ORCID platforms, and we were able to enhance our technical infrastructure and services. Such services enable interoperability between systems, create stable and reliable links between DataCite, ORCID, and other systems, and also support added value features such as citation tracking and paper claiming. These services ensure that research data are easily discoverable, accessed and shared, but also incentivise and engage researchers and motivate them to share their data, to cite properly and generally to adopt Open Science best practices.

⁵⁵ ODIN Consortium, John Kaye, Tom Demeranville, and Steven McEachern. (2013). D3.1 Humanities and Social Science Proof of Concept. Figshare. doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.824317

⁵⁶ <http://www.nshd.mrc.ac.uk/>

⁵⁷ <http://www.data-archive.ac.uk/>

⁵⁸ <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/>

⁵⁹ ODIN Consortium, Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Salvatore Mele, Sergio Ruiz, and Simeon Warner. (2013). D3.2 Proof of Concept HEP. Figshare. doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.824315

⁶⁰ INSPIRE is the main information platform for HEP, <https://inspirehep.net/>

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In the first year WP4 report, ODIN examined the necessary framework for interoperability between PIDs, establishing a conceptual model for such interoperability. The model describes key criteria for PIDs and metadata and explores relationships between different identifier schemes. The report describes how our conceptual model interacts with Linked Open Data (LOD) models and outlines several key workflows. Outside of project resources, partners have leveraged this model to create the DataCite Metadata Search, a new service available through the ORCID user interface that provides interoperability between identifiers. This service allows ORCID users to search DataCite, claim works, and import metadata into their ORCID record, demonstrating in a practical sense how PID platforms can interoperate, and validating the vision of the ODIN project.

In the second year, WP4 shifted to describing workflows for interoperability. Taken in tandem with the findings set out in this report, the WP4 uses cases contribute to the ODIN roadmap for interoperable PIDs. Our goal was to prove the value of achieving interoperability between open identifiers for data and contributors in different systems. Building upon work done in WP3, WP4 identified key use cases and examples of the practical benefits of PID interoperability. In D4.2, the ODIN partners demonstrate that PID services can facilitate linking and transfer of research information across systems, adding value to isolated pieces of information. It is clear that significant challenges remain to scale to a globally interoperable PID infrastructure. For example, adoption by researchers must continue to increase, and common workflow integrations applied across disciplines and sectors are needed. PIDs must be actively created and used, and made accessible to other infrastructure components for the Open Science vision to be realized.

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5. RESULTS FROM THE SECOND YEAR: NEW INPUT TO THE FINAL ROADMAP

In addition to the desktop research and the attendance of conferences, we interviewed six PID experts and practitioners. The interviews we conducted revealed a variety of stakeholder perspectives on research, scholarly communication and supporting services. The interviews showed very clearly that and which pieces of an interoperable PID infrastructure are missing to enable good services. Most of the experts pointed out actions that are needed, which are reflected in the recommendations presented in chapter 6. While most of the comments confirm the D5.1 findings, we were able to refine the draft roadmap and recommendations based on interviewee experiences and the results from the other two research tracks we followed. We found strong agreement across sectors and disciplines on both the vision for a trusted and interoperable PID e-Infrastructure, and what is missing to achieve that vision. The interviewees suggested similar actions and developments and confirmed the feedback gathered at conferences (presented in chapter 3) and the results from the desktop research (see chapter 4). These actions are presented alongside the gaps in the following subchapters and influence the recommendations set out in chapter 6.

5.1. National perspectives

Three of the six interviewees provided insights into their approaches to implement ORCID iDs and DOIs and their linking on a national level. Although having different levels of support from funders, national policies and infrastructure to build on, they encounter similar challenges when implementing PIDs on a national level. This echoes the feedback we gathered at conferences and confirms the gap analysis from D5.1.

“We don’t have a budget for software development; so we need someone from the Open Software community to develop a plug-in or a small patch we can re-use.”

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The main gaps identified are:

- **Lack of knowledge about national licenses or memberships** for initiatives such as ORCID⁶¹: interviewees expressed that membership models are not easy to understand and they need information on options for consortium or national licensing. National membership could assist in bringing PID services to organizations that may otherwise not be able to afford them, by providing a common platform for PID integration and service delivery. Membership models need to be accessible and affordable for small scale institutions and countries with limited funds available.
- **Lack of funding** for research infrastructure and service improvements: with ongoing cuts to library and information service budgets, there is diminishing funding for scholarly communications projects, such as implementing PIDs or improving the interoperability of repositories. Currently the focus seems to be more on having a policy on PID interoperability than actually supporting concrete implementations.
- **Lack of PID implementations into repository software**: due to the lack of funding to develop customized PID implementations, there is a huge need to have PIDs integrated into widespread repository software such as Eprints⁶² or DSpace⁶³ or publishing software like the Open Journal Systems⁶⁴. This would facilitate a wide and fast adoption of PIDs as many smaller institutions make use

⁶¹ Note that consortium membership in ORCID has been available since 2013, and the first consortium agreement was finalized about a year after the launch of the ORCID Registry. ORCID also makes provisions for national consortium membership. Agreement terms and pricing is available online (<http://orcid.org/about/membership>). These comments indicate ORCID can do more to publicise the availability of consortium licensing.

⁶² <http://www.eprints.org/>

⁶³ <http://www.dspace.org/>

⁶⁴ <https://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs/>

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of these software systems because they lack the possibilities to develop their own platform.⁶⁵

The interviewees stressed that, to fulfil the goal to make the “research information ecology” more efficient and valuable and to improve the discoverability of every research output, the following is required:

- PIDs such as ORCID iDs need to stay open and other **PIDs should ideally be opened** up or - if new ones are created - be developed collaboratively as openly resources
- Implementations should be documented and experiences need to be shared. As many developments as possible should be re-used. Although some aspects of PID implementations might not be transferable to other countries or institutions, **best practices** are useful for newcomers starting their own projects.

In addition, from the point of view of institutions and practitioners implementing PIDs on a national level, there is room for improvement in the future. PIDs should integrate provenance into data models and workflows, and should consider interactions with identity providers to support **identity management**.

⁶⁵ Note that Eprints has an ORCID wizard (see chapter 4.1.1.) available since April 2014, however, when conducting the interviews in July 2014, some interviewees expressed the need for the plug-in and were obviously not aware that it exists already. This indicates that information on the availability of such implementations could be disseminated further.

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5.2. Publisher perspectives

Publishers are the main disseminators of primary research. They have a strong interest in linking their material within and across platforms to increase the number of access points and views. However, new approaches to scholarly publishing such as open review and commenting challenges the current infrastructure and makes citation tracking more complex. Publishers are also challenged with author name ambiguity issues that impede efficient discovery, and state that in an ideal scenario, every researcher will use an ORCID iD when they submit or review a manuscript. Among the challenges expressed by publishers in the interviews and gathered through the two other methodology approaches are:

“There is no need for a researcher to know what a DOI is, but he should know how to use it.”

- **Lack of knowledge of documentation for PID integration:** especially for newer PIDs such as ORCID iDs, the implementation can appear complex with lessons learnt and best practice examples just emerging. An additional challenge is the fact that especially smaller publishers use several systems themselves and PIDs need to be integrated in all of them in an interoperable way.
- **Lack of awareness by researchers** on how to use DOIs: citation tracking is a big challenge, not only due to unclear handling of versioning, but also because researchers are not aware on how to cite data. While publishers could provide concrete citation guidelines, they prefer to adopt guidelines developed by the research community to ensure broad support.
- **Lack of incentive to provide ORCID iD with manuscript submission:** researchers lack understanding about how publisher platforms interact with ORCID and that adding the ORCID iD when submitting a paper would help interoperability and the dissemination of the correct information. They think that ORCID will know about their papers anyway.

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5.3. E-Infrastructure providers' views

E-Infrastructure providers provide the plumbing for scholarly communication. They serve the needs of specific scientific communities, implement communication standards and ideally support development of services by third-party providers. To achieve all this, they need to engage their community and related. Their use of PIDs is hindered by:

- A **DOI focused infrastructure**: DOIs are an established PID for journal articles, largely due to efforts by CrossRef. However, DOIs might not be ideal for all kinds of research output, such as versioned datasets. Thus, an interoperable PID infrastructure has to support a variety of PIDs.
- **Focus on data intensive sciences**: some disciplines are not far advanced in their use of e-infrastructures and PIDs. There is a risk that they may get ignored in the development of interdisciplinary and interoperable PID systems, but their needs should be determined and addressed.

The overarching goal of ODIN is to develop a construct for an interoperable PID infrastructure to **support scholarly communication**. This includes embedding PIDs in research outputs to support citation, linking outputs to the PIDs of researchers who created them, and further to the PIDs of organizations that supported the researchers: **person - data - organisation linking**, ideally also including PIDs that identify scientific equipment, other resources, and samples. Organisation identifiers are available, and are a mix of commercial and open resources; however data governance and interoperability between providers are outstanding issues. Standards to describe and unambiguously identify scientific equipment and resources⁶⁶ are emerging.

"We have to keep in mind that PIDs have to meet the needs of scholarly communication."

⁶⁶ https://www.force11.org/Resource_identification_initiative

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One challenge repositories will face in the future is **balancing data preservation and de-selection**. PIDs may support use cases that allow resolution to a landing page describing the de-selected data

5.4. Disciplinary challenges

Geosciences

Geosciences have a long tradition in storing and making research data accessible. It was one of the first disciplines that established data journals to publish data papers⁶⁷: detailed descriptions of a dataset that support re-use and analysis but no scientific analysis of the data itself. Whilst being advanced when it comes to using PIDs for research data, geosciences still face some challenges when it comes to linking these data PIDs to author or organisation identifiers.

“A problem is that users often do not see the value of connecting their account to ORCID. They do not understand that it make things much easier, because they think their papers are detected by ORCID anyway.”

- **Lack of incentive** to provide **ORCID iD** as part of the **metadata for research output**: although the adoption rate for ORCID iDs by researchers publishing in geosciences is rather high, they are rarely added as part of the metadata when submitting new manuscripts. Researchers are not aware of the benefits of linking data and author PIDs from the very beginning as they do not understand how different PID systems interact.

⁶⁷ Pfeiffenberger, H., & Carlson, D. (2011, January). “Earth System Science Data” (ESSD) A Peer Reviewed Journal for Publication of Data. D-Lib Magazine. CNRI Acct. doi:10.1045/january2011-pfeiffenberger

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- **Uncertainty about the financing of PIDs:** with integrating various PIDs and broadening the DOI assignment horizon to include also conference abstracts, images and figures, the question is raised who funds these PIDs and their infrastructure. Most of the geoscience data journals are Open Access and many waive Article Processing Charges and thus need support in building an extensive PID infrastructure.

Humanities and Social Sciences

We identified several gaps in PID infrastructure for the HSS community during our WP3 work with the British Library. Several of these issues were echoed in the interviews. Additional issues raised include:

- **Issues with trust and validation of third party metadata:** for a metadata curator it is difficult to evaluate whether author information coming from other sources such as ORCID is indeed accurate. This problem is more prevalent in subject repositories rather than institutional repositories, since institutional repositories can match information about researchers with additional information from their own institutional person databases.
- **Uncertainty about which PID to use:** especially in the case of appropriate PIDs for author disambiguation, it is often not clear which system should be used. There is a lack of information on how interoperable and compatible each PID is with other PID systems, but also on the features a system needs to be interoperable with others.
- **Lack of awareness of metadata requirements:** Social sciences have a long tradition of metadata standards. Humanities researchers however need guidelines and training on adapting standards that provide sufficient metadata for their research outputs or mapping their current standards to work in an interoperable

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PID environment. Ideally, this would be included in an early state of the research data management lifecycle.

High Energy Physics

Sharing publications as preprints on arXiv⁶⁸ has a long tradition in HEP. However, sharing datasets and minting them a PID is a fairly new concept. The proof of concept developed within ODIN WP3 at CERN showed a first example of how HEP data can be shared. However, we identified the following gaps:

- **Lack of interoperability between HEP platforms:** data exchange between the currently existing HEP platforms is a challenge because the discipline is without shared data management standards. This leads to inconsistencies in data models and no interoperability between platforms. In the concrete example presented in D3.2 and D3.3 this affects the DOI assignment to datasets at time of ingestion. The challenge is to identify and agree upon a standard data management workflow and PID integration points. In turn, this will encourage the development of reliable and stable ingestion methods within the community.
- **Lack of resources** for integrating sub-community platforms: a feature of HEP is a tendency from teams to develop small sub-community very specific platforms suiting particular needs for e.g. data or code sharing. While these platforms could be aggregated, more likely they will need to independently integrate PIDs. Adoption will be limited by available resources for this integration, which often is out of the scope of the building of the platform proper.
- **Lack of awareness and hesitant take-up:** HEP researchers are rarely aware of PIDs and the possibility of citing data. Unless they work across several disciplines, there is limited incentive to use PIDs. However, within ODIN, ORCID iDs and DataCite DOIs were integrated into INSPIRE, a major community platform, and

⁶⁸ <http://arxiv.org/>

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have started highlighting the advantages of PIDs, what might contribute to kick-starting of adoption.

In general, the representatives of the sectors and disciplines we interviewed agree that PIDs are relevant, beneficial, and will enable the linking of research outputs, researchers, and supporting organizations. All sectors and disciplines expressed common needs: awareness of the benefits of using PIDs on the part of researchers, and understanding of the tools and methods for integrating PIDs into workflows and systems on the part of publishers, funders, universities, and repository managers. While it may be helpful to extend our analysis more broadly across disciplines, these two needs will likely drive any PID implementation strategy.

6. THE FINAL ROADMAP - WHERE TO GO NEXT

Many of the gaps presented in chapter 5 resulting from the three-pronged research approach confirm the gaps presented in D5.1, others have been adjusted. Some of these gaps are being addressed by initiatives launched during the course of the ODIN project (see chapter 4 for an overview on implementations). Table 2 presents the final ODIN gap analysis and the progress made to close the gap to date.

“This doesn’t impact my work – this IS my work. I think every person should have an ORCID iD, not only researchers, but also staff and decision makers. All activities and output should be tracked, articles, reviews, everything.”

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Table 2: Overview of the identified gaps and the progress made to fill them

Revised gap	Progress
There is only limited access to PID e-Infrastructures for small organisations due to a lack of licenses or memberships on a national level.	<i>ORCID has expanded its public API, adding authentication, to support responsible use of ORCID by projects and small organizations. Additionally, member policies were clarified on its website.⁶⁹ Some institutions still lack the technical infrastructure or staffing resources to integrate PIDs; overcoming this may require the creation of tools or widgets that make it possible to integrate PIDs with little technical expertise.</i>
Some research communities have little to no experience with interoperable PIDs and no attempts are made to target them explicitly.	<i>There have been more PID initiatives, including direct outreach to universities and to researchers at professional association meetings, in 2014.⁷⁰ Additional work is required to communicate benefits and provide specific training to researchers.</i>
Tailored non-operable PID systems are emerging as there is no easy way to integrate interoperable PIDs in local implementations.	<i>First plug-ins to easily integrate ORCID IDs and DataCite DOIs into Eprints and DSpace and other repositories are developed to close this gap (see chapter 4.1.).</i>
There is a lack of support and funding to implement international interoperable PID solutions.	<i>Following the example of the Sloan Foundation in the US, JISC together with AMRA launched a national PID implementation initiative in the UK (see chapter 4.1.). Additional funding programmes are needed though.</i>

⁶⁹ <http://orcid.org/node/14>

⁷⁰ See e.g. <https://orcid.org/about/events> for an overview of outreach events

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Revised gap	Progress
Documentation for PID integrations is not adequately comprehensive and easily accessible and thus, the development of tools to track research data re-use is constrained.	<i>There is documentation available on e.g. the ORCID and DataCite homepages. Tracking tools are still limited. However, there are collaborations with metrics and altmetrics providers to initiate the development of more citation tools.⁷¹</i>
Policies to encourage data sharing and re-use and community specific guidelines to support them are not widespread yet.	<i>The recent developments show that on the national layer in particular measure are undertaken to foster the adoption of PIDs. University libraries increasingly provide guides and information material to incentivise researchers to use PIDs. (see chapter 4.1.)</i>
There is no discovery service for data and other non-text materials. Researchers cannot track who used data their shared and if they lead to new results.	<i>There are first integrations of PID linking that facilitate the discoverability of research data. Figshare e.g. integrated ORCID iDs and they work with ImpactStory and other altmetrics initiatives to track the DOIs they assign.⁷²</i>
Incentives and awareness to share and re-use datasets are missing.	<i>Citation counts for data citation are emerging. In addition, altmetrics get more attention⁷³ due to e.g. increased implementations of Altmetric and adoption of ImpactStory. However, there is still a lot of work to do</i>

⁷¹ <http://de.slideshare.net/datacite/2013-datacite-summer-meeting-thomson-reuters-data-citation-index-cooperation-nigel-robinson-thomson-reuters>

⁷² http://figshare.com/blog/figshare_ORCID_integration/86
<http://blog.impactstory.org/link-your-figshare-and-impactstory-accounts/>

⁷³ E.g. through an own conference <http://www.altmetricsconference.com/> or the NISO Altmetrics Project http://www.niso.org/topics/tl/altmetrics_initiative/

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Revised gap	Progress
	<i>to create more incentives and raise awareness amongst researchers.</i>
Data citation and new metrics: counting these need to be facilitated, as well as new innovative tools, services and measures.	<i>Force 11 and RDA have been making immense progress in aligning disciplinary actions to common interest groups who work heavily on these matters. Services to provide alternative metrics are more and more adopted.</i>
Unique attribution and linking between researchers, their scholarly materials, funding and institutions is impossible without a collaborative adoption of global and interoperable PID systems.	<i>This gap was confirmed in the second year of ODIN. ORCID is in contact with ISNI, Ringgold and other initiatives to increase interoperability between various PIDs and thus foster a global PID ecosystem. The RDA Persistent Identifier Interest Group will work on the coordination of these efforts.⁷⁴</i>

Following the update of the gaps and the progress made on them, our recommendations were adjusted, to provide concrete guidelines on what to do next. Table 3 shows the final refined recommendations resulting from the ODIN work as well as the acting stakeholders that are needed to put the recommendation into practise.

⁷⁴ <https://rd-alliance.org/group/pid-interest-group.html>

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Table 3: Overview of the final ODIN recommendations focused on the acting stakeholders and beneficiaries

Refined recommendations	Acting stakeholder	Beneficiary
Lower access barriers for participation to interoperable global PID e-Infrastructures e.g. through providing national licenses or other appropriate agreements.	e-Infrastructure providers ⁷⁵	e-Infrastructure providers, research communities
Broaden the scope of PID solutions to address needs of the “long tail” (less data-intensive) sciences such as the humanities and support their participation to existing interoperable PID frameworks.	e-Infrastructure providers	research communities
Facilitate interoperability between community- and/or institution-specific or national PID solutions through global open solutions.	e-Infrastructure providers	e-Infrastructure providers, funders, researchers
Provide (seed) funding to ease local access, integration and participation to emerging PID infrastructures.	funders	e-Infrastructure providers
Provide documentation for implementations and technical specifications of PID infrastructures that supports development of third-party tools for discoverability, impact assessment, and other value added services.	e-Infrastructure providers	e-Infrastructure providers, funders, researchers

⁷⁵ As stated in chapter 2, e-Infrastructure providers include data centres as well as national or institutional repositories and initiatives such as ORCID and DataCite.

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Refined recommendations	Acting stakeholder	Beneficiary
Design policies to encourage data sharing and re-use, making data a key indicator in research assessment and encourage scientific communities to support them by providing guidelines for practical implementations.	funders	researchers
The emerging global PID community needs to continue in ODIN's footsteps and develop cross-platform services, and collaborate with more stakeholders, in particular publishers and discipline-specific datacentres.	e-Infrastructure providers	Research communities, funders, publishers, e-Infrastructure providers
Provide training for researchers to raise awareness about incentive systems and good practices for data citation.	e-Infrastructure providers, publishers	researchers, funders
Concrete steps are needed to ensure the sustainability of services and tools being developed to integrate PID systems, through expansion of use by external parties and activities to foster adoption and consequently refine business models.	e-Infrastructure providers, publishers	all stakeholders
Establish a participative framework with PIDs for contributors and extend the framework and include more PIDs, e.g. for institutions.	e-Infrastructure providers	researchers, funders, scientific communities

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7. CONCLUDING RECOMMENDATIONS

In our analysis, we found some common gaps and challenges at a local, disciplinary, national and global level. e-Science and thus Open Science are not (yet) established in many areas and in particular across such boundaries. The reasons for that are many, from barriers for data sharing from different scientific cultures to technical challenges. This report focused on one aspect that could accelerate data sharing and Open Sciences as it was identified in the ODE (Opportunities for Data Exchange) project⁷⁶: persistent identifiers and understanding the barriers of their widespread adoption and technical interoperability. Annex I gives an overview table of this report's results, summarising the gaps and barriers of an interoperable PID infrastructure; the progress made up to date to overcome this barriers; and our recommended actions on how to close the gaps.

While PID experts and practitioners are aware of PID challenges but they do not know where the journey is heading to, many stakeholders are not (yet) aware of PIDs and the opportunities they offer. The "sphere of PID awareness" needs to be expanded to connect the designers and operators of e-Science infrastructures and their users in the most effective way, so to bring Open Science forward. The work of the ODIN project in the last two years has shown that this is a great challenge as implementations and initiatives evolve and support has to be continuously adapted to foster these developments:

- Technologies evolve and allow researchers to collaborate easier and faster – provided they have an infrastructure that supports their needs
- Information platforms and services are updated continuously to try to meet the researchers' needs and to test the possibilities of new technologies
- Financial considerations imply unstable or limited funding

⁷⁶ Dallmeier-Tiessen, Sunje, Darby, Robert, Gitmans, Kathrin, Herterich, Patricia, Lambert, Simon, Mele, Salvatore, Nordling, Josefine, et al. (2012). D6.1 SUMMARY OF THE STUDIES, THEMATIC PUBLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS. ZENODO. doi:10.5281/zenodo.8305

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- Policies create new incentives for researchers to participate in Open Science

Three main actions emerge:

1. Research on how interoperable PID infrastructures and services need to be delivered,
2. Participative business models that sustain PID infrastructures and foster involvement from a diverse spectrum of disciplines, institutions and countries,
3. Support for stakeholders to allow access to and participation in PID infrastructures.

There is more research needed on how to deliver concrete services based on an interoperable PID infrastructure. Given the increasing requirements requested by funders, incentives become more and more important.

- o We need to find out how to develop implementations and services that connect several PIDs with community platforms and already well-known incentive systems. At the same time, the "sphere of awareness" needs to be expanded by highlighting the importance of an interoperable PID infrastructure for these incentive systems.
- o Based on these research results, corresponding value-added service need to be build that use the PID infrastructure e.g. to track citations or new kinds of metrics and can be included in funding schemes and applications.
- o PIDs for people, their research objects and outputs and the organisations that fund this research need to be integrated into common research workflows and be easily linkable.
- o Research is needed on the verification of PID links and associated claims. Value-added services need to build on trusted information. Provenance information needs to be included in PID infrastructures to enable trust across systems and disciplines.

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- We need services that enable joint workflows for article and data linking and convey the link from submission to discovery and search services.
- All services should be developed in a way that allows easy re-use by others. Solutions should not be tailored to platforms but become portable so that they can be transferred to other systems. Services also need to be designed with scalability in mind. Seeing the rapid adoption of ORCID iDs and DataCite DOIs (chapter 4.1.1.), increasing numbers of PIDs should not be an obstacle for these services.
- We have to enable an ecosystem where others such as 3rd party services for research (e.g. open peer-review platforms) can build on top of the PID infrastructure. Some implementations exist already and were introduced in this report, but there should be opportunity for more of them to emerge. To adapt to those, an interoperable PID infrastructure has to stay nimble while being resilient at the same time. To enable this, research, experimentation, and agile feedback are needed and should be tied in closely.

These concrete services have to be delivered by a federated PID infrastructure, with concrete sustainability plans, to ensure that in the long term,

- researchers can get PIDs for themselves and their research output without barriers,
- researchers can move institutions and being assured that they can rely on the same infrastructure no matter where they work and produce these outputs and with whom they work. This has to be enabled across all EU member states and beyond.
- Institutions of all kind and size can equally participate in this PID infrastructure and thus, collaboration within member states and beyond is fostered.

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Some possible avenues are already suggested by the ODIN work:

- Adjust membership models to cover national mandates and thus, lower the barrier of participation for emerging countries
- Lower the access barrier for low income institution and consortia by e.g. introducing grants to start first PID implementations initiatives
- Investigate how such initiatives can be supported e.g. through engaging the research communities in the uptake by raising awareness for the incentives

The last action that needs to be covered is support as well for e-Infrastructure providers of all kinds who have to meet the needs of research communities and funder requirements for transparency and accountability through PIDs as also for individual researchers and research communities.

- ODIN results show that we need all kinds of support from webinars and video tutorials to on-site training sessions about lessons learned and best practices or even hackathons. In addition, better documentation and "how-to"s are needed. In addition, this support could be tailored to several disciplines, including especially niche disciplines that do not produce big amounts of data. The support is needed on several layers: technical training, financial support through e.g. grants and special funding programs and help with the organisation of dedicated training events.
- In addition, we have to raise awareness of research communities to engage them in an interoperable PID infrastructure and highlight the incentives of their participation. This can go hand in hand with establishing a culture of re-use and reproducibility and thus, take a big step towards Open Science.

In conclusion, there is a window of opportunity to design and deliver a harmonized PID e-infrastructure to deliver services to e-Science: seamlessly accessing a particular data set, automatically connecting it to the relevant researchers, easily measuring its re-use

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and impact. It can be built on the ORCID and DataCite initiative. If properly executed, with support from the scientific community, this can realise the vision of ODE project: widespread uptake of a PID e-infrastructure will accelerate adoption of Open Science by building trust through provenanced transactions and seamless **discovery** of scientific artefacts, their **attribution** to contributors and **citation** in scholarly discourse.

With proper planning, and concrete and sustained action, we can make it possible for every European researcher, at any phase of their career, within any institution in the European Research Area, to have seamless and free access to PIDs for their research artefacts and these will be uniquely attributed to them.

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8. ANNEX I: MATRIX OF REVISED GAPS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOCUSED ON STAKEHOLDERS AND BENEFICIARIES, INCLUDING A PROGRESS OVERVIEW

Revised gap	Progress	Refined recommendations	Acting stakeholder	Beneficiary
<p>There is only limited access to PID e-Infrastructures for small organisations due to a lack of licenses or memberships on a national level.</p>	<p><i>ORCID has expanded its public API, adding authentication, to support responsible use of ORCID by projects and small organizations. Additionally, member policies were clarified on its website.⁷⁷ Some institutions still lack the technical infrastructure or staffing resources to integrate PIDs; overcoming this may require the creation of tools or widgets that make it possible to integrate PIDs</i></p>	<p>Lower access barriers for participation to interoperable global PID e-Infrastructures e.g. through providing national licenses or other appropriate agreements.</p>	<p>e-Infrastructure providers</p>	<p>e-Infrastructure providers, research communities</p>

⁷⁷ <http://orcid.org/node/14>

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Revised gap	Progress	Refined recommendations	Acting stakeholder	Beneficiary
	<i>with little technical expertise.</i>			
Some research communities have little to no experience with interoperable PIDs and no attempts are made to target them explicitly.	<i>There have been more PID initiatives, including direct outreach to universities and to researchers at professional association meetings, in 2014.⁷⁸ Additional work is required to communicate benefits and provide specific training to researchers.</i>	Broaden the scope of PID solutions to address needs of the “long tail” (less data-intensive) sciences such as the humanities and support their participation to existing interoperable PID frameworks.	e-Infrastructure providers	research communities
Tailored non-operable PID systems are emerging as	<i>First plug-ins to easily integrate ORCID iDs and DataCite DOIs into</i>	Facilitate interoperability between community- and/or institution-specific or	e-Infrastructure	e-Infrastructure providers,

⁷⁸ See e.g. <https://orcid.org/about/events> for an overview of outreach events

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Revised gap	Progress	Refined recommendations	Acting stakeholder	Beneficiary
there is no easy way to integrate interoperable PIDs in local implementations.	<i>Eprints and DSpace are developed to close this gap. (see chapter 4.1.).</i>	national PID solutions through global open solutions.	providers	funders, researchers
There is a lack of support and funding to implement international interoperable PID solutions.	<i>Following the example of the Sloan Foundation in the US, JISC together with AMRA launched a national PID implementation initiative in the UK (see chapter 4.1.). Additional funding programmes are needed though.</i>	Provide (seed) funding to ease local access, integration and participation to emerging PID infrastructures.	funders	e-Infrastructure providers
Documentation for PID integrations are missing and thus, the development of tools to track research	<i>There is documentation available on e.g. the ORCID and DataCite homepages. Tracking tools are still limited. However, there are</i>	Provide documentation for implementations and technical specifications of PID infrastructures that supports development of third-party	e-Infrastructure providers	e-Infrastructure providers, funders, researchers

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Revised gap	Progress	Refined recommendations	Acting stakeholder	Beneficiary
data re-use is constrained.	<i>collaborations with metrics and altmetrics providers to initiate the development of more citation tools.⁷⁹</i>	tools for discoverability, impact assessment, and other value added services.		
Policies to encourage data sharing and re-use and community specific guidelines to support them are not widespread yet.	<i>The recent developments show that on the national layer in particular measure are undertaken to foster the adoption of PIDs. University libraries increasingly provide guides and information material to incentivise researchers to use PIDs. (see chapter 4.1.)</i>	Design policies to encourage data sharing and re-use, making data a key indicator in research assessment and encourage scientific communities to support them by providing guidelines for practical implementations.	funders	researchers

⁷⁹ <http://de.slideshare.net/datacite/2013-datacite-summer-meeting-thomson-reuters-data-citation-index-cooperation-nigel-robinson-thomson-reuters>

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Revised gap	Progress	Refined recommendations	Acting stakeholder	Beneficiary
<p>There is no discovery service for data and other non-text materials. Researchers cannot track who used data they shared and if they lead to new results.</p>	<p><i>There are first integrations of PID linking that facilitate the discoverability of research data. Figshare e.g. integrated ORCID iDs and they work with ImpactStory and other altmetrics initiatives to track the DOIs they assign.⁸⁰</i></p>	<p>The emerging global PID community needs to continue in ODIN's footsteps and develop cross-platform services, and collaborate with more stakeholders, in particular publishers and discipline-specific datacentres.</p>	<p>e-Infrastructure providers</p>	<p>Research communities, funders, publishers, e-Infrastructure providers</p>
<p>Incentives and awareness to share and re-use datasets are missing.</p>	<p><i>Citation counts for data citation are emerging. In addition, altmetrics get more attention⁸¹ due to e.g.</i></p>	<p>Provide training for researchers to raise awareness about incentive systems and good practices for data citation.</p>	<p>e-Infrastructure providers,</p>	<p>researchers, funders</p>

⁸⁰ http://figshare.com/blog/figshare_ORCID_integration/86

<http://blog.impactstory.org/link-your-figshare-and-impactstory-accounts/>

⁸¹ E.g. through an own conference <http://www.altmetricsconference.com/> or the NISO Altmetrics Project http://www.niso.org/topics/tl/altmetrics_initiative/

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Revised gap	Progress	Refined recommendations	Acting stakeholder	Beneficiary
	<i>increased implementations of Altmetric and adoption of ImpactStory. However, there is still a lot of work to do to create more incentives and raise awareness amongst researchers.</i>		publishers	
Data citation and new metrics: counting these need to be facilitated, as well as new innovative tools, services and measures.	<i>Force 11 and RDA have been making immense progress in aligning disciplinary actions to common interest groups who work heavily on these matters. Services to provide alternative metrics are more and more adopted.</i>	Concrete steps are needed to ensure the sustainability of services and tools being developed to integrate PID systems, through expansion of use by external parties and activities to foster adoption and consequently refine business models.	e-Infrastructure providers, publishers	all stakeholders

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Revised gap	Progress	Refined recommendations	Acting stakeholder	Beneficiary
Unique attribution and linking between researchers, their scholarly materials, funding and institutions is impossible without a collaborative adoption of global and interoperable PID systems.	<i>This gap was confirmed in the second year of ODIN. ORCID is in contact with ISNI, Ringgold and other initiatives to increase interoperability between various PIDs and thus foster a global PID ecosystem. The RDA Persistent Identifier Interest Group will work on the coordination of these efforts.⁸²</i>	Establish a participative framework with PIDs for contributors and extend the framework and include more PIDs, e.g. for institutions.	e-Infrastructure providers	researchers, funders, scientific communities

⁸² <https://rd-alliance.org/group/pid-interest-group.html>

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9. ANNEX II: BRIEFING SHEET FOR INTERVIEWEES

What this is about

There will be no Open Science without researchers' buy-in. Recent studies highlight that researchers' engagement is still rather limited or uneven across disciplines and subfields and that incentives need to reach a tipping point in open sharing and reuse of scholarly materials. The most effective incentives relate to scholarly metrics: those used in career and research assessments, as well as new, emerging, informal ones.

The ODIN project is based on the vision that the actual implementation and success of such incentive mechanisms is depending on a reliable infrastructure and service framework with persistent identification. Today, it appears that there are several gaps to realize this vision. This can be seen in the first ODIN results presented after the first year in deliverable D5.1 Gap analysis and draft roadmap⁸³.

ODIN wants to dig deeper to detect missing actions which are required for an interoperable persistent identification framework.

As part of this, ODIN conducts interviews with a series of experts active in scholarly communication, to detect the most prominent gaps for individual stakeholder groups and disciplines and the impact of these gaps. The multi-stakeholder and interdisciplinary approach shall ensure the broad, but detailed applicability of the outcome.

This document provides you, the interviewee, with a short background about the work of the ODIN project and its approach. It shall help you and us setting the scenes for our conversation about persistent identification and the facilitation of Open Science. This will then feed into ODIN's final recommendations to the EC.

⁸³ Consortium, ODIN; Dallmeier-Tiessen, Sünje; Herterich, Patricia; Mele, Salvatore (2013): D5.1 Gap analysis and draft roadmap. figshare. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.825546>

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The ODIN Project

ODIN is a 2-year funded project by the European Commission under the umbrella of the 7th Framework Programme. ODIN's partners are ANDS (Australian National Data Service), arXiv, British Library, CERN, DataCite, Dryad and ORCID. ODIN focuses on the interoperability and future of persistent identifiers for data and researchers across the entire ecosystem of scholarly communication. ODIN partners represent the broad spectrum of stakeholders active in scholarly communication, with no disciplinary boundaries, with partners of the exact sciences, the natural sciences and the social sciences and humanities.

www.odin-project.eu

The interviews

The interviews will inquire about our forthcoming work with persistent identification for scholarly materials and their authors/contributors. We would like to understand how we can overcome the obstacles and provide better support for adopters of PID systems.

Thus, we are particularly interested in any kind of training you are aware of, have participated or maybe even organized when it comes to DOIs, ORCIDs or other persistent identifiers.

We have already gathered a list of gaps and recommendations. At the end of the interview, we would like you, as the experts in the field, to comment on these and, if applicable, highlight the potential impact on your individual work.

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Questionnaire

About the interviewee:

Institution/Company:

Position:

Responsibility/Job description:

Specific to a scientific discipline, if applicable:

Questions:

1. General information about PID use

- a)
 - a. Where and how do you use PIDs in your work?
 - b. Which PIDs do you use? [DOIs, ARK, Handle, author identifiers, grant/funder information]
 - c. Where do you get your PIDs from and why? [Crossref, DataCite - are you member or not, same for ORCID or any other author ID] Was it difficult to get PIDs or get reliable information about them?
 - d. How many of them are implemented in your system already?
- b) If you don't use PIDs yet, why so? Do you plan to implement them in the future?

2. Progress of PID implementation

- a) How far/well are PIDs integrated in your institution/system?
- b) What supported the implementation? [Are there guidelines relevant to you that recommend PID implementation? policies, funding,...] Did you get "external" help?
- c) What are the main challenges/ strongest barriers? [technical, organisational, financial,...]
- d) Where would you need support for a better or easier implementation? By whom?

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- e) Are you collaborating with other institutions/initiatives to improve implementation?

3. Use of PIDs for metrics/citation tracking

- How are PIDs in your implementation/platform linked? [E.g. authors - publications - data - grant links] Do you have any plans in that regard?
- Does your platform/implementation encourage reuse/citation of scholarly materials other than text/papers, i.e. research data or code?
- Do you (intend to) show citation stats for material/records? If not, what are the main obstacles?
- Do you consider other metrics/statistics? If yes, which ones?

4. Training/support

- Did you attend any workshops, meetings, trainings by any PID provider before you got started?
- Did you consult dedicated training material (online or print)? If so, which one? Please provide details?
- Are you training your researchers/clients/partners in any PID related activity?

5. Future scenarios

- What would be your ideal case scenario for PID implementation in 5 years/10 years? How would this impact your work?
- Where do you think you could learn from other disciplines/stakeholders regarding implementations?

	D5.2 Final roadmap and recommendations for the missing thin layer of the e-Infrastructure		
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ODIN gaps and recommendations

Gap 1: There is only limited access to PID e-Infrastructures for small organisations.

→ **Action 1:** Lower access barriers for institutions to participate to interoperable global PID e-Infrastructures, through appropriate agreements between institutions, fostering collaborations and with the support of national/international bodies.

Gap 2: Some research communities have little to no experience with interoperable PIDs for data and contributors.

→ **Action 2:** Support those scientific communities without existing PID solutions to participate to existing interoperable PID frameworks, while tailoring interfaces to the specificity of the community.

Gap 3: Local, tailored, PID systems, with no interoperable options, are emerging.

→ **Action 3:** Facilitate interoperability between stakeholders with community-specific, institution-specific or national PIDs solutions and emerging global open solutions.

Gap 4: There is a lack of support and funding to implement international interoperable PID solutions.

→ **Action 4:** Provide (seed) funding to ease local participation and access to emerging PID infrastructures.

Gap 5: Methods and tools to track re-use of research data and other scholarly materials are lacking.

→ **Action 5:** Develop an interoperable PID infrastructure that supports development of third-party tools for discoverability, impact assessment, and other value added services.

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Gap 6: Policies to encourage data sharing and acknowledge data re-use in research assessment are not yet widespread.

→ **Action 6:** *Design policies to elevate data to a key indicator in research assessment, with appropriate attribution to their creators and curators, through implementation and usage of open and interoperable PIDs.*

Gap 7: Reliable discovery services for research data and non-text based scholarly materials are missing.

→ **Action 7:** *Harmonize formats and APIs, so that information from emerging and existing PID frameworks can be exposed and mutually enriched, while enabling third-party discovery services.*

Gap 8: Incentives for making datasets re-usable are unclear or missing.

→ **Action 8:** *Design appropriate incentive systems to pervade research evaluation, e.g. citation mechanisms based on PIDs for data, linked to PIDs for contributors.*

Gap 9: Value-added services that can incentivize citation and open science cannot be built for lack of a widespread, interoperable, PID infrastructure.

→ **Action 9:** *Assure that a trusted, open and sustainable interoperable PID infrastructure is established with ease of participation of third-parties.*

Gap 10: Unique attribution and linking between researchers, their scholarly materials and funding is just not possible, without a collaborative adoption of global and interoperable PID systems.

→ **Action 10:** *Establish a participative framework with PIDs for contributors and materials, where any participant can expose information, enriching the entire e-Infrastructure.*

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Three main tiers to address the gaps identified so far

1. Deliver an interoperable PID layer for data and contributors of the highest quality, fostering participation of all existing early adopters. A high standard is crucial to enable adoption and assure development of third-party value-added services; these, in turn, support incentives for researchers and others parties to adopt PIDs. A crucial element of this tier consists of building support and training elements that enable every European participant to benefit from reliable PID infrastructure and services.

2. Promote and support multi-stakeholder research on missing aspects of a global PID e-Infrastructure and services. Dialogue between stakeholders identifies features in need of development by a party, benefiting the other, furthering third-party adoptions. Examples are advanced disambiguation systems, PIDs for entities beyond researchers, new metrics systems, global integration of PIDs to a longer tail of scholarly outputs.

3. Design and implement sustainable and participative business models to lower the participation barrier for entities to embrace a global PID e-Infrastructure, while assuring a resilient operation and prevailing openness.

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10. ANNEX III: LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ADS	Archaeology Data Service
ARMA	Association for Research Managers and Administrators
CRIS	Current Research Information System
DIGOIDUNA	Digital Object Identifiers and Unique Authors Identifiers to Enable Services for Data Quality Assessment, Provenance and Access
DoW	Description of Work
HEI	Higher Education Institute
HEP	High Energy Physics
HESA	Higher Education Statistics Agency
HSS	Humanities and Social Sciences
ISNI	International Standard Name Identifier
LOD	Linked Open Data
NISO	National Information Standards Organization
NSHD	National Survey of Health and Development
ODE	Opportunities for Data Exchange
OR	Open Repositories
PID	Persistent Identifier
PMC	PubMed Central
RDA	Research Data Alliance
UKDA	UK Data Archive
WGS	World Geodetic System